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Effect of Computer-Based Animation Instructional Packages on Senior Secondary School Students' Interest and Achievement in Agricultural Science in Gboko Metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria

H. A. ALABI, Charity Wanger AKAA and Adoo Blessing WOMBO

Department of Agricultural Education, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of computer-based animation instructional packages (CBAIP) on senior secondary school students' interest and achievement in Agricultural Science in Gboko Metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria. Four research questions were asked, and four hypotheses were formulated. Quasi experimental design, specifically pre-test post-test control group design, was adopted. The population of the study is 2,505 while the sample size was 160 SSII Agricultural Science students, which was drawn from eight secondary schools (four private schools and four public schools), using purposive sampling techniques. In each of the schools, intact classes were randomly assigned to experimental and control groups. The research instruments used were Agricultural Science Achievement

Test (AAT) and Agricultural Science Interest Inventory (AII). These were face validated by five experts, trial-tested and used for data collection. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was used to get the reliability of AII which was 0.65 and Kuder-Richardson formula 21 was used to determine the reliability coefficient of AAT which was 0.87. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, using Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). In the course of the field work four (4) instruments were misplaced. Therefore, the study had 156 instruments to work with. The results of research showed that there was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Agricultural Science using CBAIP and students taught with the chalk board method. There was no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students taught Agricultural science with CBAIP and students taught with the conventional method. There was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students in public schools taught Agricultural science using CBAIP and their counterpart in private schools. There was also no significant difference between the mean interest rating of students in public schools taught Agricultural science using CBAIP and those in private schools. This study therefore recommends that because computer animation instructional strategy promotes Agricultural Science students' achievement, Agricultural Science teachers should be encouraged to adopt the instructional strategy for the teaching of Agricultural Science in secondary schools.

Keywords: Computer-Based Animation Instructional Packages, Agricultural Science Education, Conventional Teaching, Interest, Achievement, School Type

Introduction

Agriculture has remained the largest sector of the Nigerian economy that plays a significant role as food provider, employer of labour and foreign exchange earnings. It contributes about 31% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), with crops accounting for 87%, livestock 7%, fisheries 4% and forestry 2% (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2011). Agriculture also employs over 51.3% of the labour force in Nigeria and accounts for 70% contribution to the non-oil sector (Achike & Ichoku, 2011). The significance of agriculture to national growth has made the teaching of agriculture at all levels of our educational system a continuous practice. According to Onu *et al.* (2014,) Agricultural Science is largely the application of scientific principles for successful production of crops and livestock, and other uses for man's benefit.

Owing to the role agriculture plays in nation building, it is important for the subject to be well taught and understood by students so as to maximize the benefit it has to offer. Teaching Agricultural Science is a transfer of knowledge and skills, which must be done using modern innovations in order to meet the emerging needs of the present time. The teaching of Agricultural Science in secondary schools has the following aims: to stimulate and sustain students' interest in agriculture, to enable students acquire basic knowledge and practical skills in agriculture, to prepare students for further studies in agriculture, to prepare students on basic scientific knowledge and attitudes required for entry into agricultural occupation (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). The abovementioned aim is likely to be a mere wish if the instruction in agriculture is not handled with the appropriate teaching approaches or methods.

The conventional method of teaching Agricultural Science in Nigerian secondary schools seems ineffective in developing the needed technical knowledge and acquisition of the vocational skills necessary for agricultural development as stated in the National Policy on Education. The mode by which teacher presents instruction affects response from the students and determines whether they are interested, motivated and involved in a lesson in such a way as to engage in a good learning or not (Mtsem, 2011). The inadequacy of the chalk board method to improve students' interest and achievement has become a source of concern to many educators. What constitutes the 21st century skill for teachers is the use of appropriate technology, content and pedagogy in the classroom.

One of the innovations that could influence and is still capable of enhancing knowledge delivery is the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) (Ziden *et al.*, 2011). ICT has the potential to transform the way instructions are delivered. Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP) is one of the ICT alternative strategies for teaching. It is useful in facilitating teaching and learning science and environmental education concepts. Computer animation in the view of Owolabi *et al.* (2019) is simply bringing inanimate objects to life on a screen. Giginna (2013) explains that it is an ICT-based teaching strategy. Researchers discovered that when animation was used for objects included in the explanation of a particular concept, learning increases. For every hour a teacher speaks, only about 8 – 10 minutes of the information given is retained in the students' mind. The rest of the information is lost as learners tend to lose interest and attention to the content being presented, especially when the lesson is dull and gloomy (Thomas, 2013). However, when visual aids are used, it raises the interest of the learners.

Interest is seen as the psychological state of getting an effective reaction to any topic of focus. Gimba (2013) in his own view defined interest as an excitement or feeling accompanied by special attention to doing something. One way to enhance student's interest is by creating an engaging, meaningful environment where students are able to discover the value in what they are learning (Iorliam *et al.*, 2021). Djudin (2018) also found that both internal and external factors are responsible for students' interest in learning. The internal factors relate to the students' attitude, skills, knowledge, aspirations (hope), assumptions, goals and so on whereas the external factors relate to the environmental conditions including teaching and learning resources, type of school, infrastructure and management practices. Akram *et al.* (2017) reported in a study on student interest in Chemistry that students in public schools were more interested in Chemistry courses as compared to their peers enrolled in private schools. From this it can be said that the type of school (public or private) a student attends affects their interest in learning regardless of the subject and consequently their achievement in that subject.

The term "academic achievement" has been defined by many scholars. Parveen *et al.* (2013) defined academic achievement as the knowledge attained, and skills developed in school subjects. Academic achievement, according to Ejesi (2014) is the outcome of education – the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has attained their educational goals.

To arrest students' attention, interest, and curiosity and promote their achievement, the use of activity-stimulating and student-centered approaches like digital learning instead

of depending on the conventional teaching approach needs to be embraced. It is against this background that the present study seeks to determine the effect of computer-based animation instructional package on the interest and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Agricultural Science in Gboko Metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria.

Objectives

The specific purpose of the study was to investigate:

- i. the effect of Computer-Based Animation Instructional Package on Students' Interest in Agricultural Science in Senior Secondary Schools.
- ii. the differences in the Interest of Students in Public and Private Schools when taught with Computer-Based Animation Instructional Package and when taught with the chalk board method.
- iii. the effects of Computer-Based Animation Instructional Package on Students' Academic Achievement in Agricultural Science in Senior Secondary Schools.
- iv. the differences in the Academic Achievement of Students in Public and Private Schools when taught with Computer-Based Animation Instructional Package and when taught with the chalk board method.

Research Questions

Based on the specific objectives of this study, the following research questions were answered by the study:

- i. What are the mean interest ratings of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method?
- ii. What are the mean interest ratings of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method?
- iii. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method?
- iv. What are the mean achievement scores of students in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and are tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method.

- iii. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method.
- iv. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with the chalk board method.

Methodology

The study adopted quasi-experimental design. Majorly, the design was non-randomized pre-test post-test non-equivalent control group design. This design is selected because it establishes a cause and effect between dependent and non-dependent variables. In this study, intact classes were randomly assigned to the experimental and control groups. The experimental groups were for computer-animation package while the control group was for the chalk-board method.

The study was carried out in Gboko metropolis of Benue State, Nigeria. Gboko is one of the largest and most populous towns in Benue State. It has a landmass of 2,264 sq.km with a population of over 400,000, mostly Tiv people. It is bounded by Tarka Local Government on the North, Ushongo Local Government to the South, Buruku Local Government on the East, Gwer on the West and Konshisha Local Government on the Southwest. The population of this study consists of 2,505 senior secondary school Agricultural Science Students (SSII) from thirty-five (35) government approved secondary schools in Gboko metropolis (Source: Teaching Service Board, Makurdi). The sample size for the study is 160 SSII students. Eight (8) schools (four private schools and four public schools) are sampled using purposive sampling techniques.

Two instruments were used for data collection in this study namely: Agricultural Science Achievement Test (ASAT) and Agricultural Science Interest Scale (ASII). The ASAT consists of two sections, section A contains the background information of the respondents, that is; class, time allowed and type of school. Section B contains all the multiple-choice questions that tested the student achievement. The questions selected were based on the instructional objectives as contained in the SSII Agricultural Science curriculum. ASAT consists of 30 items which are multiple-choice objective questions with four options (A B C and D) from which the students were expected to pick the option they consider correct. The total mark obtainable from the ASAT is 60 marks, as one question attracts two marks. The ASII, positively and negatively worded, was measured on a four-point interest scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) to enable the students to indicate their level of interest. It was used for both the pre-test and post-test.

The instruments for the data collection were face validated by five experts; one from Measurement and Evaluation, one from Agricultural Extension Education and Communication, one is from the Department of Vocational Agriculture and Technical Education, all in Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi Nigeria; an Agricultural Science teacher from Calvary Arrows College Gboko and an ICT Specialist. The experts were to check the instrument to ascertain their suitability to what they are to measure as highlighted

in the objectives of the study. Corrections made by the experts were used to review the instruments before use. The corrected instruments after validation were used for a trial testing in a secondary school in Wanune town, which was not part of the sample for this study. 16 SSII students were used for the trial testing. The trial testing was done to determine the internal consistency of the instruments collected from the ASAT which was analyzed using Kuder-Richardson formula 21 to determine the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.87. The choice of KR-21 was because of the dichotomy nature of the scores from ASAT. Cronbach Alpha was used to check the reliability of the ASII, which yielded 0.65 alpha values.

The researchers and one research assistant from each school used for this study administer the pre-test to the students that participated in the study. Thereafter, the teacher assisting in the study taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP to the experimental group and conventional chalk board method were used on the control group. The whole process lasted for four weeks after which a post-test and post-CBAIP were administered on the students again. Mean and standard deviation scores were used to answer the research questions. Analysis of Covariance was used to test the formulated hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. ANCOVA was chosen because of the fact that it removed the differences across the non-randomized groups. For the hypotheses, when the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected, but when the p-value was less than 0.05, null hypothesis was rejected.

Results

The results are presented in line with the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What are the mean interest ratings of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of interest scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method

<i>Group</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>			<i>Post-Test</i>		
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean Gain</i>
<i>CBAIP</i>	78	37.15	4.72	41.65	3.46	4.50
<i>Chalk board Method</i>	78	37.20	3.86	40.93	4.01	3.73
<i>Mean Diff</i>		0.05		0.72		0.77

Table 1 shows the mean interest scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught without CBAIP. The result shows that the pre-test interest scores for those taught using CBAIP and Chalk board method had mean scores 37.15 and 37.20 respectively. The mean difference of 0.05 shows that the two groups are at the same

cognitive level before the post-test examination. Moreover, the students who were taught Agricultural Science using CBAIP Method had mean score of 37.15 with a standard deviation of 4.72 at the pre-test and a post-test mean score of 41.65 and standard deviation of 3.46. Also, students who were taught Agricultural Science using Chalk board Method had mean score of 37.20 with a standard deviation of 3.86 at the pre-test and a post-test mean score of 40.93 with a standard deviation of 4.01. Mean gain scores of 4.5 and 3.73 for the two groups of learners respectively, indicating that those who were taught Agricultural Science using CBAIP Method had higher post-test mean score than their counterparts who were taught using Chalk board Method.

Research Question Two

What are the mean interest ratings of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation of interest scores of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method

School type	Teaching Method	Pre-test			Post-test		
		N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean Gain
Public	CBAIP	40	36.19	2.96	41.73	3.75	5.54
	Chalk board method	40	38.03	3.51	40.79	3.93	2.76
Private	CBAIP	38	38.17	4.10	41.57	3.86	3.40
	Chalk board method	38	36.33	4.06	41.08	4.15	4.75

Table 2 shows the Mean and Standard deviation of interest scores of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method. The table shows that students from Public schools who were taught Agricultural Science using CBAIP method had mean score of 36.19 with a standard deviation of 2.96 at the pre-test and a post-test mean score of 41.73 and standard deviation of 3.75. Also, students from private schools who were taught Agricultural science using CBAIP method had mean score of 38.17 with a standard deviation of 4.10 at the pre-test and a post-test mean interest score of 41.57 with a standard deviation of 3.86. The mean gain scores of 5.54 and 3.40 for the two groups of learners respectively indicate that the learners from public schools who were taught Agricultural Science using CBAIP method had higher post-test mean score than their counterparts from private schools who were taught using the same method. Moreover, the post-test standard deviations of 3.75 and 3.86

for the two groups respectively imply that those from the private schools who were exposed to CBAIP method varied more in their individual scores than their counterparts exposed to the same instructional method from the public schools.

Furthermore, learners exposed to CBAIP method from the public schools with mean gain of 5.54 and those taught with the conventional chalkboard method with mean gain of 2.76 show that those taught with CBAIP had a higher post-treatment interest. However, learners exposed to CBAIP method from the private schools with mean gain of 3.40 and those taught with the conventional Chalkboard method with mean gain of 4.75, an indication that those taught with CBAIP had a lower gain than those taught using the chalkboard method.

Research Question Three

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of achievement scores of learners taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method

Group	Pre-Test			Post-Test		
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean Gain
CBAIP (Experimental)	78	19.45	5.62	21.03	5.12	1.58
Chalk board Method (Control)	78	19.63	5.08	19.90	4.98	0.27
Mean Diff		0.18		1.13		1.31

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of achievement scores of learners taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method. The result shows that in the pre-test, students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP had a mean score of 19.45, while the students taught Agricultural Science with the chalkboard method had a mean score of 19.63. The mean score difference in the pre-test is 0.18 indicating that the two groups are at the same cognitive level before the treatment. In the post-test, the students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP had a mean score of 21.03 while the students taught with the conventional chalkboard method had 19.90. The mean score difference between the two groups is 1.13 in favour of those taught with CBAIP. Moreover, the mean gains for those taught Agricultural Science using CBAIP and the chalkboard method are 1.58 and 0.27 respectively.

Research Question Four

What are the mean achievement scores of students in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of achievement scores of learners in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP

School type	Pre-Test			Post-Test		
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean Gain
Public	78	18.48	6.68	20.08	6.33	1.60
Private	78	20.47	4.07	22.03	3.19	1.56
Mean diff		1.99		1.95		0.04

Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviation of achievement scores of learners in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP. The result shows that the pre-test achievement scores for those taught Agric using CBAIP method in the public and private schools in Gboko had mean scores 18.48 and 20.47 respectively. The mean difference of 1.99 shows that the two groups are about the same cognitive level before the treatment. Moreover, the post-test achievement mean scores of students who were taught Agricultural Science in the public and private using CBAIP Method are 20.08 and 22.03 respectively. The mean gains in the public and private schools are 1.60 and 1.56 respectively. The closeness of the gains in the public and private shows that the two groups are at the same cognitive level after the application of treatment.

Testing of Hypotheses

The data for testing the hypotheses is presented in Tables 5 to 8.

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method.

Table 5: ANCOVA Result of Interest of Students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalkboard method

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-test Interest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1.291 ^a	3	.430	1.861	.139	.035
Intercept	189.819	1	189.819	820.950	.000	.844
Pre-Test Interest	.984	1	.984	4.258	.041	.027
Teaching Method	.275	1	.275	1.190	.277	.008
Teaching Method * Pre-Test Interest	.468	1	.468	2.024	.157	.013
Error	35.145	152	.231			
Total	450.000	156				
Corrected Total	36.436	155				

a. R Squared = .035 (Adjusted R Squared = .016)

Table 5 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of F (1.190) for the effect of teaching method on students' interest in Agricultural Science is 0.277. Since the probability value of 0.277 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with conventional chalkboard method.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method.

Table 6: ANCOVA Result of Interest of Public and Private school of Students taught Agricultural science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-test Interest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	.856 ^a	3	.285	1.219	.305	.023
Intercept	193.435	1	193.435	826.364	.000	.845
Pre-Test Interest	.752	1	.752	3.215	.075	.021
School type	.037	1	.037	.159	.691	.001
Pre-Test Interest * Schooltype	.016	1	.016	.067	.796	.000
Error	35.580	152	.234			
Total	450.000	156				
Corrected Total	36.436	155				

a. R Squared = .023 (Adjusted R Squared = .004)

Table 6 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of F (0.159) for the effect of school type on students' interest in Agricultural Science is 0.691. Since the probability value of 0.691 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk board method.

Table 7: ANCOVA Result of Achievement Scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with conventional chalkboard method

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-Test Achievement						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7.260 ^a	3	2.420	13.422	.000	.209
Intercept	431.354	1	431.354	2392.358	.000	.940
Pre-Test Achievement	4.141	1	4.141	22.966	.000	.131
Teaching Method	3.758	1	3.758	20.841	.000	.121
Pre-Test Achievement Teaching Method	.018	1	.018	.100	.752	.001
Error	27.406	152	.180			
Total	468.000	156				
Corrected Total	34.667	155				

a. R Squared = .209 (Adjusted R Squared = .194)

The result of the Analysis of Covariance presented in table 7 shows that the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.005 level of significant at 1 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that the test is significant. The result implies that there is statistically significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with conventional method.

Ho: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with the chalk board method.

Table 8: ANCOVA Result of achievement scores of students in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-Test Achievement						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	8.173 ^a	3	2.724	15.630	.000	.236
Intercept	432.939	1	432.939	2483.880	.000	.942
Pre-Test Achievement	2.928	1	2.928	16.798	.000	.100
School type	.084	1	.084	.480	.489	.003

Pre-Test	4.596	1	4.596	26.367	.000	.148
Achievement *						
School type						
Error	26.494	152	.174			
Total	468.000	156				
Corrected Total	34.667	155				
a. R Squared = .236 (Adjusted R Squared = .221)						

Table 8 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of F (0.480) for the effect of school type on students' achievement in Agricultural science is 0.489. Since the probability value of 0.489 is greater than the .050 level of significance ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis was retained or accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP. Besides, the partial Eta Square value (effect size) of .003 shows that CBAIP instructional approach had low effect on the achievement of students in Agricultural science.

Discussion

The result of the study in Table 1 and 2 shows that there is a mean difference between the mean interest ratings of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalkboard method. The findings give credence to what was earlier observed by Aiyedun (2020) who reported that animation teaching was viable in upgrading students' achievement, retention and interest in climate change. The result of this study is also in line with the findings of Muhammad *et al.* (2017) who said that animation could be interesting and have the power to gain the attention and interest of the learners for hours together without boring them. This was said to be helpful to learners since it possesses features that aid in learning difficult concepts that ordinarily would not have been possible.

The results of the study in Table 3 and 4 revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of Public and Private school students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP. This finding is opposed to that of Djudin (2018) who found that both internal and external factors are responsible for students' interest in learning. The internal factors relate to the students' attitude, skills, knowledge, aspirations (hope), assumptions, goals and so on whereas the external factors relate to the environmental conditions including teaching and learning resources and the type of school. The result is also not in consonance with Akram *et al.* (2017) who reported in a study on student interest in Chemistry, stating that students in public schools were more interested in Chemistry courses as compared to their peers enrolled in private schools. We can therefore conclude that the school environment of a learner, whether public or private, does not necessarily affect their interest in learning. But what is important is the internal factors which relate to the students' attitude, skills, knowledge, aspirations (hope), assumptions, goals and the teacher.

The answer to research question three is in Table 5 above. The result indicates that there is a statistically significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those taught with chalk-board method. This

result is in line with the findings of Bamidele and Yoade (2017), that animation combined with narration and on-screen text package produced the highest mean score, followed by the animation combined with narration package and the lowest mean score was recorded for the conventional teaching method. From their experiment, they concluded that computer Animation Instructional Packages are more effective in enhancing students' achievement. Gupta and Lata (2014) also noted that animation led to the improvement in students' achievement in science better than the lecture method.

The answer to research question four is provided in Table 7 and 8. The result shows that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students in public and private schools taught Agricultural Science with CBAIP and those. The result of this finding is different from the report of Mohammed *et al.* (2017) who said that the type of schools a learner attends has profound influence on his academic achievement. Also, Bibby and Peil in Mohammed *et al.* (2017) noted that children who attended private schools perform better than pupils in public schools. The reason for the equal performance of the students in both schools could be as result of the kind of teacher found in private schools. In some private schools, the teacher teaching in public school is also the same person that is engaged in public school, so the possibility of the students performing alike is likely.

Conclusion

The study examined the effect of computer-based animation instructional packages on senior secondary school students' interest and achievement in Agricultural Science in Gboko metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria. The findings reveal that students exposed to computer-based animation instruction significantly outperformed their peers taught with the chalk board method. This indicates that computer-based animation instructional packages are an effective instructional strategy for enhancing students' engagement and understanding in Agricultural Science.

However, the study found no significant difference between the interest and achievement of public and private schools students taught Agricultural Science with animation instructional package and those taught with the chalk board method. This indicates that animation instructional package benefits them equally and does not affect their interest.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study and their implications for education:

- i. Agricultural Science teachers should incorporate Computer-Based Animation Instructional Package in their teaching since the strategy improves students' achievement in Agricultural Science.
- ii. School Administrators should organize training that are aimed at equipping teachers with necessary skills required in the use of animation in their lesson.
- iii. Curriculum planners and textbook authors should include Computer Based Animation in Agricultural Science curriculum and textbooks as complimentary to other teaching methods.

- iv. Ministries of education, State Secondary school Education Board and other Educational stakeholders are encouraged to promote the use of Computer Based Animation Instruction in schools by organizing conferences, seminars workshops for serving teachers to update themselves on the use this strategy.

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